

PATIENTS WITH "SERORESISTANCE" IN THE WOUND BIOCHEMICAL INDICATORS IN BLOOD

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Abstract. *It should be noted that one of the biggest challenges in venereology is seroresistance in wounds. Despite the use of new treatment, this condition frequently arises in patient and causes social and psychological problems. Our current research is based on the factors that led to the development of this situation.*

Keywords: *seroresistant Wound healing, Venereology, Biochemical testing, Protein metabolism, Urea levels, Creatinine levels, Glucose levels, Primary diagnosis, early latent wound, Primary seropositive lesion, Secondary lesion, Neurotoxicity, Wound infection.*

Introduction

Many scientific studies have been done on the topic of wound care, and among professionals and scholars working in the field, there is a general consensus that individuals receiving treatment for the condition are becoming more resistant to healing. Biochemical testing holds significance when it comes to wounds exhibiting seroresistance.

The registration of wound diseases in Uzbekistan has decreased annually in recent years. Early forms of the disease are getting less frequently registered, whereas relatively late and early hidden variants are becoming more common in terms of overall prevalence.

Blood samples from patients with seroresistant lesions were subjected to biochemical tests. The patients were categorized based on their primary diagnosis as follows: primary seropositive lesions – 12 patients (9%), secondary (new and recurrent) lesions – 44 patients (33%), early latent – 67 patients (50.3%), late latent – 8 patients (6%), and neurotrauma – 2 patients (1.5%).

We determined that it is unnecessary to elaborate further, as the full characteristics of the observed seroresistance condition in patients have already been provided above.

Purpose of the Study. The aim of the study was to investigate the effects of biochemical testing before and after therapy in wounds with seroresistance, while considering the primary diagnosis.

Materials and methods of research. Biochemical tests were conducted on the blood of 133 patients with seroresistance syphilis at the RIDV and KIAT centers, as well as in Almazor Inter-district TTKD in Tashkent. The text highlights that certain biochemical parameters, such as albumin, lipids, bilirubin, and alpha-amylase are low in the blood of patients with seroresistance ulcers. Total protein, urea and creatinine levels were also examined in the patients.

After analyzing the total protein levels in the blood of 128 patients with lesions that were resistant to treatment, the findings were contrasted with those of the control group and normal parameters.

When seroresistance was detected, the mean total protein in treated patients with a primary seropositive lesion diagnosis was 75.2 ± 1.2 g/L, which was greater than that of the control group (72.6 ± 0.6 g/L), but remained within the normal range.

Patient with an initial diagnosis of seroresistance with secondary lesion had a higher total protein level (76.4 ± 1.0 g/L) than the control group (72.6 ± 0.6 g/L).

Table 1

Groups of patients	Total oxygen (g/l) (n = 128)	Urea (mmol/l) (n = 121)	Creatinine (mmol/L) (n = 19)
Normal indicator	65 – 85	2,5 – 8,3	0,044 – 0,1
Control group	72,6 +- 0,6	5,4 +-0,22	0.059, +- 0,002
Primarily seropositive lesion (n=12)	75,2 +-1,2 P < 0,02	5,1 +- 0,24 P < 0,02	0,053 +- 0,002 P < 0, 002
secondary (n = 44)	76,4 +-1,0 P < 0,02	5,2 +- 0,15 P < 0,2	0,057 +- 0,002 P < 0,2
Early forms (n = 67)	76,1 +- 0,7 P < 0,001	5,35 +- 0,15 P < 0,5	0,058 +- 0,002 P < 0,5
Late forms (n = 8)	77,1 +- 1,2 P < 0,01	5,8 +- 0,25 P < 2	0,061 +- 0,002 P < 0,2
Neurosis (n = 2)	76,2 +- 0,7 P < 0,02	5,37 +- 0,25 P < 0,3	0,059 +- 0,002 P < 0,2

In comparison to the control group (72.6 ± 0.6 g/L), the blood of 67 seroresistant patients whose major diagnosis was “early latent wound” exhibited a slightly higher total protein level of 76.1 ± 0.7 g/L.

After being diagnosed with “late latent wound” seroresistant individuals had the highest total protein concentration in their blood (77.1 ± 1.2 g/L) when compared to the control group (72.6 ± 0.6 g/L).

The total protein content in the blood of seroresistant patient with a primary diagnosis of neuroinjury (2 cases) was 76.2 ± 0.7 g/L.

Total protein fractions were not included because they were studied in a small number of patients.

The findings of the biochemical tests on total protein show that the body’s ability to metabolize protein is more negatively impacted by the length of time it is exposed to the wound associated with the primary diagnosis, perhaps leading to the development of seroresistance. This is due to the “specific” inflammatory process that the wound infection requires.

Some components of nitrogenous waste (urea and creatinine) were studied in the remaining cases: urea in 121 patients and creatinine in 119 patients with seroresistant

wound conditions. The obtained results were compared with indicators from the literature and with those of the control group (18 healthy individuals).

Urea levels in the blood are normally 2.5–8.3 mmol/L, while in our control group, the average urea level was 5.4 ± 0.22 mmol/L. When we use the primary diagnosis to interpret the result, we get the following image.

After the primary diagnosis of "seropositive lesion" in patients with seroresistant lesions, the urea level was slightly lower at 5.1 ± 0.24 mmol/L, which was also lower than the control group (5.4 ± 0.2 mmol/L).

Patients with "secondary wound" and the last seroresistant condition had a lower blood urea level (5.2 ± 0.15 mmol/L) than the control group.

Seroresistant patients with the primary diagnostic of "early latent wound" had a blood urea level of 5.35 ± 0.15 mmol/L, higher than the control group's level of 5.4 ± 0.22 mmol/L.

Urea levels in the blood of seroresistant patients diagnosed with "late latent wound" showed a higher result of 5.8 ± 0.25 mmol/L (control group: 5.4 ± 0.22 mmol/L).

The blood urea level of seroresistant patient who were diagnosed with "neurotoxicity" was 5.37 ± 0.25 mmol/L.

As a result, among the primary diagnosis, individuals with seroresistance ulcer in the "late latent wound" group had slightly higher blood levels of several nitrogenous waste components, particularly urea.

Before further therapy, creatinine, another nitrogenous waste component, was examined in the blood of 119 patients who met the criteria for seroresistance status. The creatinine level in the control group (18 healthy persons) was 0.59 ± 0.002 mmol/L, whereas the literature indicates that creatinine levels are normally 0.044 ± 0.01 mmol/L.

The creatinine level in the blood of seroresistant patients with a primary diagnosis of "primary seropositive lesion" was 0.053 ± 0.002 mmol/L. Although this level was within the normal range, it was lower than the values in the control group.

The blood creatinine level in 44 seroresistant individuals with a main diagnostic of "secondary wound" was 0.057 ± 0.002 mmol/L, greater than in the control group.

There was no significant difference in the creatinine level between the control group's diagnostic of "early latent wound" and the blood of the 67 patients with a main diagnostic of "early latent wound" and a seroresistance state (0.058 ± 0.002 mmol/L).

The creatinine level in the blood of 8 seroresistant patients with a primary diagnosis of "late hidden wound" was higher than that of the control group (0.053 ± 0.002 mmol/L), at 0.061 ± 0.002 mmol/L.

The creatinine level in the blood of 2 seroresistant patients with a primary diagnosis of "neurotoxicity" was observed to be the same as that in the control group (0.059 ± 0.002 mmol/L).

Taking everything into consideration, we felt that it was reasonable to highlight the outcomes of various indicators and biochemical test findings in some circumstances. It should be mentioned that all biochemical results were acquired prior to the patients with SR receiving further medication. There were 18 healthy people included in the control group.

In conclusion, it can be observed that in patients with SR, the effect of chronic inflammation resulted to a greater creatinine level the longer the wound infection persisted in the body. This is because the nitrogenous waste's components, creatinine and urea, have a longer-lasting influence on the patient's body.

The components of the metabolism of carbohydrates: glucose test results. One aspect of the metabolism of carbohydrates is glucose, which was examined in the blood of 120 patients who had seroresistant wounds. Depending on the type of lesion, patients with seroresistant diseases had glucose levels ranging from 2.2 to 8.5 g/L. The literature states that 3.5–6.1 g/L is the normal range for glucose. The average glucose level in the control group (18 healthy adults) was 4.35 ± 0.27 g/L.

Conclusion It is important to remember that wound seroresistance is one of the most urgent issues in venereology. Despite the application of new therapeutic techniques, patients frequently experience this condition, which results in psychological and social problems.

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